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ABSTRACT

WP11 reviews new developments on energy-efficient and sustainable accelerator concepts, fostering related technologies and strategies for operation through networking and collaborations. Technologies with potential for improving energy efficiency include efficient RF power sources, power converters and power quality compensators, accelerator magnets based on permanent magnet material, superconducting cables and magnets. Another focus was set on overarching ecological concepts, which is a rapidly evolving issue in the global RI field and need further development. It will help identify the most promising directions of R&D and to formulate best practices for the construction of new facilities, thus supporting all other part of this WP11.

WP11 also includes the design and prototype construction in industry of an efficient klystron RF power source as a replacement for LHC, and the development of Permanent Magnet (PM) combined magnets that could dramatically decrease power consumption of future storage-ring based synchrotron light sources.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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1 Motivation

Particle accelerator driven research infrastructures (short: RI’s) present powerful facilities for fundamental research. Besides performing basic research, several research applications provide direct input for the development of environment friendly technologies, or the transition to renewable energies. On the other hand these facilities consume significant amounts of grid energy, and their construction is associated with a carbon footprint. While basic research is an indispensable part of the progress of society, it is at the same time important to look for the most sustainable solutions for the conduct of this research.

Definitions of sustainability include ecological, economical and societal aspects. For example the cost of a research infrastructure should be reasonable as well, and so one has to find the right balance of all aspects.

In this activity of I.FAST selected topics were considered that have the potential to improve the energy efficiency of particle accelerators and to reduce the impact on the environment. Energy efficiency is of course a key aspect for facilities with large grid power demands. But there are other sustainability aspects to be considered, from carbon footprint of the construction over water consumption to lifecycle management and heat recovery, to name a few.

2 Efficient RF Sources, N. Catalan-Lasheras

The energy consumption of the radio Frequency systems in an accelerator is a sizable fraction of the total value. For electron machines and in particular for Higgs factories, this is on the order of 40-60% for the FCC case, 38% for CLIC. It is then of the utmost interest to increase the efficiency of RF sources feeding warm or superconducting accelerating systems.

A first workshop on the efficiency of RF power sources used in accelerators was organized on July 2022 and took place in Chateau de Bossey near CERN, Switzerland [01]. (). Thirty-six participants register to the event that was made in Hybrid form to accommodate COVID travel restrictions still in place at the time. Twenty-one presenters introduced the state of the art on RF usage in labs around the world and the latest initiatives in the design and use of RF sources designed to decrease the wall-power needed to run accelerators. Two years after and by popular demand, a second workshop was held in Toledo, Spain (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/1407353/>), From this two workshops, we will summarize a number of important conclusions that depict the current status of the field.

2.1 HIGHER EFFICIENCY KLYSTRONS DEVELOPMENTS

The efficiency of a klystron is measured as the ratio between RF power extracted at the output of the klystron and the beam power transferred to the electron beam, which is simply calculated as beam current times voltage. The input RF power is negligible and measured in Watts. The current efficiency observed in tubes commercialized for science can be observed as blue dots in Figure 1. Most of these tubes lay well below what is called the industrial empirical limit. In recent years, new klystrons designed for high efficiency have been prototyped, manufactured and tested bringing the empirical line consistently 10% over the previous value.

Figure 1: Beam power to RF efficiency of klystrons used for science against their microperveance. Traditional tubes are shown as blue points while new designs focusing on high efficiency are shown in green, Light green filled symbols represent prototypes still in production.

All three klystron manufacturing companies in the world (CANON, CPI and THALES) have produced high efficiency prototypes and have even included them in their catalogue. In some cases, this has been a common effort between institutes and industry as in the collaboration CERN-THALES partially funded by EU inside the iFAST program. Fast progress comes from IHEP in China, where the RF sources for CEPC are being developed with energy efficiency in mind.

2.2 OTHER HIGH POWER SOURCES.

Solid state amplifiers and in particular the use of GaN on SiC transistors has seen an impressive development in recent times. Not only this technology allows its use at higher frequency (up to S-band) but the single transistor power is now rated at the kW level. High power combiners open the way to MW RF sources based on solid state.

More sophisticated and faster simulation and optimization software has greatly encouraged improvement studies. Power sources based on magnetron, inductive output tubes (IOT) or solid state, have been thoroughly described and discussed in the two workshops. Cross pollination between new ideas with the same objective in mind has generated and advanced concepts like the KLYNAC or the recent TRISTON aimed at the FCC project.

2.3 AUXILIARY SYSTEMS AND OPERATION

When looking at the global RF system efficiency, the parameter space on which the system is operated is very important. Efforts in XFEL, ESRF or CERN have demonstrated the potential to save up to 20,30, 50% of the energy spent on the system without any impact on performance. Peripheral systems like the high voltage generator, the solenoidal focus power supply or the waveguide network finally connecting to the cavities has a mayor impact, especially in pulsed power for Linacs. The use of permanent magnets as solenoids, optimized HV pulses or shorter lines needs to be included in the equation.

Figure 2:left: AC consumption of RF stations in kW in XFEL after several improvements in operation. Right: efficiency of the LHC klystron for two different working points.

2.4 MORE EFFICIENT USE OF THE AVAILABLE RF POWER

Downstream from the power sources, the conversion of RF power into beam power is the final step on the chain with non-negligible impact on the electricity bill. The example of the CLIC damping rings is illustrated in the following pictures. The recent optimization of the accelerating structure used for the machine is subject to very high beam loading and allowed to reduce the energy consumption of the damping rings from 54 to 10MW. The corresponding infrastructure to cool this cavity is also reduced and comes down from 32 to 25 MW. All factors accounted for, the full CLIC-380 GeV complex power consumption is reduced by more than 30% This is an inspirational example of design for sustainability that should encourage everybody on the field of accelerators to design not only cost effective but also energy effective components.

Figure 3: Power consumption of the CLIC 380GeV design, left before and right after the optimization of the damping RF system.

3 High Efficiency Klystron for LHC, N.Catalan-Lasheras

The initiative to design and build a high efficiency klystron to be used in the LHC as a demonstrator was launched in 2018. Simulation packages developed at CERN predicted an RF power to beam-power efficiency of 70% for a new optimized CERN design, using the same power converter and infrastructure in use in the LHC. A collaboration with THALES (FR), the manufacturer of the original klystron was established to convert one unit that is currently in use in LHC into a high-efficiency model, while reusing most of the ancillary systems like the solenoid, support frame, output window, vacuum window and gun. The new model is fully compatible with the installation at CERN without major modifications, so it can be used as a spare for the LHC machine. A view of the old and new klystron (reference TH2167 and TH2167HE) can be seen in Figure 4 with the associated table of nominal parameters. Thales chose to aim for a more conservative result of > 65% efficiency based on its own simulations.

Figure 4 view of the original and upgraded tube. A third harmonic cavity was added, penultimate cavity was relocated and the collector was redesigned.

Table 1: Parameters of both tubes agreed between CERN and Thales.

	TH2167	TH2167HE
Power [kW]	300	350
Frequency [MHz]	400.8	400.8
Gun microPerveance	1.65	1.65
Beam microPerveance	0.7	0.7
Cathode voltage [kV]	58	58
Anode Voltage [kV]	≤35	≤35
Beam current [A]	8.5	9
Efficiency [%]	60	≥65
Gain [dB]	≥37	≥37
Bandwidth [MHz]	±1	±0.7
Group delay [ns]	130	≤250

The kick-off meeting for this work took place in September 2021. After twelve months of re-design efforts both from CERN and Thales the design converged into the version shown in Figure 4. A preliminary design review took place in October 2022 to freeze the design. Besides the necessary changes in the klystron body to increase the klystron efficiency, it was decided to re-design and rebuild the collector to increase the safety factor of the original model. The solenoid was separated in two different circuits to increase flexibility, which requires the addition of a second power supply.

Manufacturing drawings became available during 2023 and two more reviews were organized by Thales to verify the interfaces and validate the final drawings.

The brazing of the last two cavities into what is called the vehicle test was an important step in the fabrication that required a stop point and a discussion between Thales and CERN before continuing the work. Another stop point was the tuning of the second and third harmonic cavities.

Besides re-building the tube, a series of adaptations was required to bring the klystron and its ancillary systems to the current, more strict regulations applicable today. The new klystron is equipped with Harting’s HAN Q2 electrical connectors and improved grounding. Additional lead shielding was designed and procured to reduce radiation and prevent direct contact with high radiation parts. New calculations were done for the mechanical load of the frame statically and during the rotation between vertical and horizontal position used for transport. The final klystron was fully assembled by July 2024 when it was installed in the test bench at Thales.

Initially aimed at being a proof of principle, it became apparent during the project that the new beam parameters expected from the high luminosity LHC upgrade will benefit from a higher power per klystron. The high-efficiency model is indeed able to produce 350 kW instead of 300 by using the same electrical power. Tests at the factory have demonstrated a maximum power of about 365kW with an enhanced efficiency of 70% as per design (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Left:measured power (orange line and empty dots) superposed to the efficiency (blue line and dots) simulated using the KlyC code developed at CERN along the powering curve of the tube. The green line represents the original, more conservative Klys2d simulations Right: picture of the measurement devices in Thales showing a maximum power of 364.8 kW for an input power of 61.4W. The scope below shows the absence of sidebands that will indicate a dysfunction of the tube.

The prototype arrived to CERN on October 30, 2024 and is currently connected to the test bench waiting for final validation tests before launching the construction of the remaining units necessary to run HL-LHC.

4 Power Converters, A.Sunnesson

All research infrastructures use power converters, and these can be more or less efficient. Given the amounts of energy that RIs consume, the efficiency impacts the overall sustainability of the site. Another way to improve sustainability can be to use solar panels to cover some of the energy consumption. Since RIs generally occupy a lot of real estate, the installed solar power can be quite substantial, even compared to the energy use by most RIs.

Generally, Research Infrastructures now are designed with sustainability in mind – cooling systems, electrical installations and so on normally have provisions for sustainability either by smart recycling of excess heat, planning for solar panels, or some other measure that reduces the carbon footprint of the facility. An example of how ESS has been presented is shown in Fig. 6.

The rising energy costs poses a significant challenge for research organizations, impacting the operational duration of accelerator facilities. To counter this, many facilities are taking a strategic approach, spreading the risks of price volatility through in-house production, storage, price hedging and, as a last resort, selling waste heat. This goes hand in hand with efforts to improve efficiency since the most effective way to counter energy cost is to spend less.

This chapter will go into what sub-task 3 has achieved. We will touch on solar panel work, smart heat recovery at different sites, sustainability implementation at different infrastructures, and advances in power conversion [1].

Figure 6: Schematic depiction of ESS without smart heat recovery and with smart heat recovery ([2], Eldvall, iFAST workshop).

4.1 CERN EXAMPLE

At CERN, considerable progress has been made on sustainability by considering all aspects of cooling and power converters. Several energy efficiency initiatives are running. See [3] for examples. These are, among others:

- i) Heat recovered is injected into the heating system in a local community
- ii) Building within the CERN complexes are heated by recovered heat in various ways
- iii) Several improvements are discussed and implemented to improve LHC cryogenics efficiency (LHC cryogenics is a major part of CERN energy consumption)
- iv) In the East Area Experimental Complex, a project for efficiency was delivered 2021. The energy use was reduced from 10.85 GWh/y to 0.66 GWh/y by pulsed powering. At the same time water used went from 21900 cubic meters to 1337 cubic meters yearly
- v) For the North Area, all power converters are planned to be replaced until 2033. Optimisation and improvements are expected to yield up to 50% energy use reduction
- vi) FCC plans include plans for efficiency and energy storage to improve efficiency (novel topologies, capacitors, batteries, flywheels, fuel cells, and gravitational storage)

Figure 7: Schematic depiction of CERN local heat recovery scheme ([3], Nisbet, iFAST workshop)

4.2 ESS EXAMPLE

ESS has worked on efficient heat recovery and solar power. Already, the power converters powering the accelerator are very efficient. On top of this (though not part of iFAST), ESS is working on a strategy to optimize energy supply. [4]

4.2.1 Heat recovery

ESS was planned and designed with sustainability in mind – the cooling system does not use a conventional cooling tower. Rather, the excess heat from the operations is recovered as much as possible to the district heating system, and to a local system heating the office and lab houses.

ESS was designed to allow heat recovery with three different temperature regions for the cooling water. This makes recovery more efficient, and ESS is already selling heat to the district heating provider. One future goal is to have the highest temperature cooling water to provide heat directly to the local grid – today heat pumps are required, with a penalty in efficiency.

At ESS, a Central Utility Building (CUB) controls the temperatures and flows of the cooling water. No cooling tower is present, rather all excess heat is sold to the district grid.

Three temperature levels are employed: Low (around 10 degrees C); Medium (around 20 degrees C); and Warm (40 degrees C and upwards). This allows optimisation of the cooling flows depending on the use – warm cooling water is for example employed for the klystron collectors, and this water can reach temperatures of 65 degrees C or more. This is used to sell heat. The lower temperature circuits are employed via a local grid to heat the ESS premises. So, during operations, ESS will receive all its heat from the facility itself.

The system is depicted in Fig. 8. In the left half, the cooling water flow is depicted, moving between the central utility building and the equipment in three separate streams. In this half, the excess heat is recovered. In the right half of the figure, the destinations/uses of the heat is indicated.

Figure 8: Schematic depiction of ESS cooling system ([2], Eldvall, iFAST workshop).

4.2.2 Solar power

Since all large facilities occupy significant amounts of real estate, the land surface can be used for energy generation. ESS has made extensive calculations on the possibilities on the ESS site. Even with the relatively northern latitude, south Sweden has more than 50% of the potential of Sahara for PV generation. Using the PVGIS model, it has been shown that already covering the accelerator berm (10 MW installed power) could account for between 5 and 10% of ESS total energy needs (current estimate 270 GWh annually). Covering more of the area occupied by ESS would increase the fraction that will be covered. Adding battery storage could further improve the possibilities. This is considered in the FlexRICAN EU program, outside iFAST.

ESS also considered the direct injection of PV generated DC power into its power converters, particularly the modulators. This allows skipping the DC/AC converter from the solar panels and the AC/DC conversion at the input of the modulator. Removing these two steps means the efficiency could be improved by up to 6 percentage points. Given the vast amounts of energy used, this could certainly be useful. It would require designing an efficient 1.1 kV DC/DC converter to match the ca 400 V output from the solar panels to the internal 1.1 kV voltage of the modulators (Fig. 8).

As estimates show, saving up to 500 MWh per year is possible for 10 MW installed peak power.

Figure 9: Example of how PV direct injection could save power (for example [4], Sunesson et al)

4.3 MAGNET POWER CONVERTERS

For magnet power converters a lot of progress has been made in recent years when it comes to control, accuracy, and sustainability.

At PSI new dipole supplies for the synchrotron light source are designed, and will soon be introduced. The specifications include very fast swing and dual voltage requirements. Very tight control of the waveforms is required.

To meet the specifications, the requirements were split in DC and AC parts and stacked PI controllers were employed. Very precise control was achieved by the concept.

Further, the lifetime of the converters could be greatly improved by addressing “power cycling”, that results in mechanical forces due to thermal cycling, reducing the IGBT lifetime. New IGBT types and better thermal management have helped to improve this. Newer IGBTs exhibit at least a ten-fold increase of the power cycling capability. Fig. 10 depicts a typical bond wire set-up. The issues occur where the bond wire meets the chip, due to cycling and different thermal expansions. Improved soldering techniques, temperature monitoring, and switching to copper bond wire rather than aluminium are examples of mitigating techniques.

Figure 9: Schematic depiction of bond wire set-up in IGBTs ([6]. R. Künzi, iFAST workshop)

Elettra presented another work, the design of Magnet Power Converters for Elettra 2.0 (Elettra upgrade). Elettra was a partner to ESS and delivered magnet power converters to ESS, and the experience from this project was very useful for the design of magnet power converters for the Elettra upgrade. For these powerconverters footprint, availability, and sustainability were key concerns [7].

As a result of the development it was possible to equip the new Elettra synchrotron with only 3 different types of converters. Standardization was employed as well.

The designs yielded impressive results for current ripple, stability, and efficiency. For example, the current ripple was suppressed by a factor 20 below specifications. In Fig 11 an example of a ripple measurement is given. After compensating a disturbance, the measured ripple is 4 ppm/FS, compared to the specification of 100 ppm/FS.

Figure 10: Current ripple measurement in converters ([7], Caetero, iFAST workshop)

5 Cross Linking Accelerator R&D with Industrial Approaches, P. Spiller, T. Winkler

5.1 RELEVANCE OF SUPERCONDUCTING ACCELERATOR TECHNOLOGIES FOR FUTURE ENERGY SYSTEMS

A workshop on superconductivity and sustainability with special attention to possible applications for energy systems and particle accelerators has been conducted at GSI in 2023. "Superconductivity and Sustainability" was the motto of a future-oriented workshop held jointly by the GSI SIS100/SIS18 department, headed by Dr. Peter Spiller, and the European superconducting industry association "CONNECTUS", chaired by Wolfgang Walter from Bilfinger Noell. The aim of the workshop was to improve communication between the particle accelerator community and the superconducting industry and to present the latest developments in both areas. Numerous well-known European companies and representatives of public institutions took part in the event.

GSI and FAIR are among the largest manufacturers of superconducting accelerator magnet systems in Europe. This made it necessary for GSI to build up outstanding expertise in the field of superconducting systems during the preparatory project phase. Today, GSI is in contact with all relevant European suppliers. There is great potential for European research laboratories and European industry to apply new innovative concepts for greater sustainability and energy efficiency to accelerators and thus qualify them for future use in energy systems in public and private facilities.

At the workshop (Fig. 12), there was a lively exchange on the demand for further improvement of key parameters and performance. Studies and developments to increase the energy efficiency of large

accelerator facilities and for energy systems in the public sector were presented. A key topic were synergies in the development of future superconducting technology with regard to its application in particle accelerators and energy systems. The I.FAST program ("Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology"), where GSI/FAIR is involved in several work packages, provided the framework and motivation for the workshop. I.FAST is an EU-funded program that aims to advance new developments in the field of accelerator-based research infrastructures and promote innovative technologies. GSI's contributions to the project include the development of new superconducting cables and approaches for the sustainability and energy efficiency of particle accelerator facilities.

Figure 11: Group photo of the workshop on “sustainable energy systems and accelerator research and development”

European energy supply systems as a whole are undergoing major change, which requires the development and application of new technologies. Superconductivity can play a key role, particularly with regard to the conversion of energy systems. At present, energy transported in liquid, solid or gaseous form are predominantly used to supply a large proportion of the energy required by our society, and these are mainly transported in pipe systems and tanker trucks. A planned switch from chemical to electrical energy sources would require enormous amounts of energy to be transported by cable (i.e. the existing electrical grid infrastructure) in the future. However, high line losses and restrictions are to be expected, which could potentially be avoided with transportation in superconducting energy cables. The issues of increasing transport capacities in electrical transmission systems shows up on the level of long distance transport, e.g. in the 380 kV European power grid, but also locally in short distance transmission systems working on low voltage levels directly serving private and industrial consumers. However, so far the focus of first application studies for superconducting energy transport systems is clearly on the long distance transport and high voltage and high power systems.

GSI and collaborators are presently developing a new generation of cable serving future fast ramped s.c. accelerator magnets (see EU IFAST WP8). The layout of the new cable replaces the NbTi strand of the known Nuclotron cable technology by HTS tapes. The magnets using the Nuclotron technologies are usually operated at 4.5 K. In this cable the superconducting NbTi-strands are wrapped around a CuNi tube which is cooled by a two phase forced helium flow. In the frame of the EU I.FAST program, the know-how for technologies of fast ramped s.c. magnets and dedicated cables is further strengthened. The motivation for this development is the performance needed for the potential next generation of fast ramped synchrotrons and its magnets. The new general trend in using HTS technologies shall also serve the goal of enhancing the energy efficiency of the next generation of accelerators and thereby enable a more economic operation. Especially fast ramped s.c. synchrotrons, often used in high repetition operation or as injectors for larger synchrotrons or colliders, with their enormous amount of dynamic loss and heat induced into the cryogenic system determine the energy consumption of the cryoplant. JINR, Dubna is operating the superconducting Nuclotron synchrotron. JINR is planning a major modification of its LTS magnet system. In the frame of a largely completed R&D phase, JINR has developed a modified Nuclotron cable based on HTS tapes wound around the central cooling channel instead of the NbTi strands. Using HTS for the Nuclotron cable allows higher coolant temperatures and the use of other liquids and gases. Besides other options, the yokes of the new Nuclotron magnets will potentially be cooled by boiling N@80 K and the coil by gaseous He at 50 K. JINR has also explored ion beam treatment of HTS tapes and succeeded to enhance the critical current density. By exchanging all LTS magnets by the new HTS magnets, the energy cost for operating the NICA cryoplant shall be reduced by more than ten times. The approach of developing HTS cables for the next generation of synchrotrons is also a core R&D activity at GSI. In collaboration with IEE Slovak Academy of Science, the ILK, Dresden and EMS University of Twente a round high current low AC loss ReBCO cable is under development. The AC loss in an HTS Nuclotron cable in an external magnetic field, e.g. in a coil of magnet is dominated by hysteresis loss. The hysteresis loss increases with the width w of the tape.

$$Q_{HT} = \frac{2}{\pi \cos \alpha} B_{max} I_c w$$

At the ramp rate needed for a FAIR SIS400 dipole cycle, with about 373 W/m, the AC loss would become unacceptable high. To lower hysteresis loss, several attempts have been performed in industry to substructure HTS tapes in smaller filaments, e.g. by laser cutting, mechanical cutting or etching. A new development of the company Supra for making striated HTS cables with filament widths of less than 0.1 mm may become a new opportunity to enable high ramp rates. Experimental studies applying the new striated HTS tapes to the HTS Nuclotron cable are in preparation. Furthermore, the application of such a new cable technology for energy transport in AC electric grids will be investigated.

Figure 12: Development of Nuclotron cable technologies. Left: Standard cable with NbTi strands, second left: Nuclotron cable with HTS strands (copyright A. Shemchuk), third left: EU I.FAST winding tests for an HTS Nuclotron cable, right: Sketch of a low loss filamented HTS Nuclotron cable.

As a next step, GSI will study the advantages of the above described, low loss (AC) s.c. cable for applications in energy systems. One issue of s.c. energy transition cable is the re-cooling of the cable over long distances and the efficiency of the corresponding cryogenic system. Lowering the AC loss by means of a filamented cable may also have a positive impact in a three-phase electrical transmission system where each cable is under the influence of the magnet field of its neighboring cable.

Current developments at GSI/FAIR and CERN as well as other technologies for future particle accelerators are providing significant impetus in this regard and can therefore be used for the benefit of society. In particular, major advances in the mass production of high-temperature superconductor materials and price reductions will enable large-scale applications in the future. In the context of the presently enhanced momentum for developing technologies for magnetically confined fusion plasma, several private start-ups have been created which often lack experienced technical staff, expertise and skills. The technical capabilities of research institutions, however, are usually concentrated in technical departments that have generally existed for decades. Thus, a collaborative support of the private activities by public institutions may significantly enhance the probability for success and maintaining schedule expectations in this area. Such collaborations finally may end up in a win-win situation since private investments usually rely on larger capital. An example is the envisaged collaboration between Proxima Fusion and GSI in respect of the development of a prototype s.c. HTS coils for generating magnetic confinement. GSI has decided to support an application of Proxima Fusion by providing its know-how in the area of quench detection systems and instrumentation. Beyond quench detection and electrical parameter monitoring systems, GSI's expertise also includes low temperature and strain measurements, which are essential aspects in the design and testing of s.c. magnet systems. Meanwhile, several other collaborations between public research organizations and start-ups have been formed in the development of fusion for energy systems.

The topic of sustainability is a key issue for GSI and FAIR. Thus, it is of particular interest to highlight approaches for reducing the energy consumption of large-scale plants in the medium term. For example, replacing copper coils, which result in higher energy losses due to energy dissipation, with superconducting coils can decrease the energy consumption of beam guidance systems (see next chapter). Other technological approaches for lowering the energy consumption of accelerator based research facilities are:

- Energy Saving HTS Magnets
- Energy Saving s.c. Linacs
- KI based Power Grid Monitoring System

- Sensor Based Energy Monitoring System
- Watchdog for Accelerator Devices
- Development of an HTS Nuclotron Cable with potentially increased coolant temperature
- FAIR Energy Consumption Prediction
- Cooling Water Flow Control
- Energy Efficient Design of SIS100 and FAIR Cooling System
- Energy Efficient beam transport by High Current Pulsed magnets

The question of how cooperation between accelerator centers and industry can be intensified in the future was also of particular importance at the workshop. There was a consensus that the development of high-tech products requires long-term cooperation and the early involvement of industry. In order to optimize this, suitable adjustments to the legal framework conditions are useful. A working group of the I.FAST program is dealing with precisely these questions. The result should be a guideline for the early and long-term involvement of industry in the development of accelerator centers.

5.2 REDUCING THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION BY MEANS OF ENERGY SAVING ACCELERATOR MAGNETS

Initial situation

Assuming normal user operation of the accelerator facility (approx. 6000 - 7000 operating hours per year), approximately 56% of GSI's annual energy consumption is caused by the accelerator system. Beam guidance magnets and the UNILAC linear accelerator RF systems are the main contributors to the heavy ion accelerator's energy consumption. The effective power of the GSI accelerator systems is around 11 MW (UNILAC: approx. 4.5 MW, SIS: approx. 3 MW, HEBT: approx. 1.4 MW, ESR: 2 MW (varies greatly depending on the operating mode)). The magnets of the beam transport system account for around 10% of the energy consumption of the accelerator system. Of the energy dissipated in the magnet, around 3% is released into air and 97% into cooling water. In addition to the energy dissipation in the magnets themselves, there are resistive losses in the supply lines/cables and the power supplies. In addition, there is the heat from the cables and power supplies, which is mainly released into the air. The share of losses is divided into around 70-80% magnet, 5-15% cable and 10-20% power supply. The heat generated must be dissipated by the technical building equipment. For this purpose, recirculation cooling devices and cooling water circuits are used, the electrical motors of which and pumps must be added to the energy balance of the magnet system. The savings potential of the following proposal must be estimated in detail, considering the entire system. The savings potential is presumably around 10% of the total energy consumption of the GSI.

Superconducting magnet coils

Unlike the copper coils of conventional beam guidance magnets, no energy is dissipated in superconducting coils. However, the magnet's cooling system must dissipate the heat introduced into the cold system, consisting of a static and dynamic part. The energy required for cooling, i.e. for dissipating the heat introduced from the superconducting magnet system, decreases as the coolant temperature increases. The required coolant temperature depends primarily on the transition temperature of the superconducting material used and can be significantly higher, especially when using high-temperature superconductors (HTS), than with "conventional" superconductors such as

NbTi. The energy required to cool a superconducting coil is significantly lower than the energy required to operate conventional copper coils. As a result, the operating costs of the accelerator system can be reduced if superconducting coils can be developed replacing the copper coils of the conventional magnets (Fig. 14). Replacing the copper coil with a superconducting coil is technically easy to implement, as the magnet yokes are always divided into multiple parts. For example, the upper half of the yoke of a dipole magnet can always be lifted off and the coil removed. The use of liquid or gaseous coolants LHe/GHe and LN/GN should be avoided, as this would require the construction of a new, complex technical infrastructure with a central cooling system, distribution and transfer systems. Furthermore, the introduction of energy-saving technology would be difficult, as the infrastructure would first have to be built. Instead, coil systems cooled by a cold head are preferable, which can be set up locally. Consequently, the use of standard s.c. cable technologies such as Nuclotron- or Rutherford cables would not be optimal. Instead, "pancake" coils (Fig. 15) and coils in the form of a wound HTS tape are preferable.

Figure 13: CAD view of the iron dominated magnet with cryostat system (left) and cold mass (right)

Figure 14: HTS pancake coil with current leads

In a first step, a concept study was carried out to a) analyze the optimal coil configuration, b) to determine the optimal coil position and c) calculate the heat load in a conservative, high load operation approach and minimization of eddy current heating. In our study a maximum ramp rate of 0.5 T/s has been determined as limit for the cooling, generating a correspondingly high dynamic load to the cryogenic system (Fig. 16).

Figure 115: Assumed operation cycle for an HTS energy saving magnet

On the basis of the "pancake" coil shown, it is difficult to implement coil offsets to minimize the stray field. It must therefore also be checked whether there are configurations in which the influence of the stray field is negligible. Furthermore, it must be checked whether the static and dynamic losses introduced into the coil can be dissipated via a cold head using line cooling. In our case study, a maximum power consumption of 14 kW by two cryo coolers was targeted. Depending on the magnet cycle, only one cryo cooler with corresponding lower consumption may serve the requirements. This is the case for magnets which are not continuously ramped during operation (e.g. stationary beam line magnets).

A solid body or internal bath cooling can be used as line cooling. Since the GSI beam guidance magnets are operated at relatively low field strengths (<1.9T), it has been studied whether the required number of ampere-turns can be produced in a sufficiently small coil volume in such a way that volume is created for line cooling and the cryostat container. In addition, it must be clarified whether a quench detection and protection system is required for individual coils and the correspondingly low stored energy. If the development of a superconducting replacement coil is successful, the conventional copper coils could be gradually replaced from shut-down to shut-down.

Power supplies

Ideally, the design of the s.c. coil should be chosen so that the product of the number of turns and current corresponds to the original copper coil. Otherwise, when replacing the coils, all power supplies would also have to be purchased and replaced. The resistance visible through the power supplies would be reduced to the resistance of the supply lines/cables. The current in dipole magnets of the GSI HEBT magnets is usually 400-600 A. In addition, the effect of an s.c. coil without any resistance on the control behavior of the existing power supplies must be examined. The inductance is crucial for the ripple, but also the control of the devices, which is related to the load resistance. Depending on the PC circuit variant used, problems can arise with lower current values, if the load resistance is low (compared to the original design).

Drawback

With the result of our engineering study, first cost estimates for the manufacturing of the cryostat system, the HTS coil and the cold head with compressor have been conducted. It can be concluded that the procurement of these components exceeds the procurement costs of the conventional dipole magnet by about a factor 3.

6 Ecological Concepts, D.Völker, A.Klumpp

The overall sustainability of an accelerator based research infrastructure is a complex theme with the energy efficiency representing the most important aspect. But Sustainability for RIs comprises of much more than energy efficiency. Materials, expendable items, gases and other ecological concepts are equally important. The method of environmental impact assessment along the life cycle of an RI provides a good basis to identify the most promising directions of R&D and to formulate best practices for the construction of new facilities. But in many cases the solutions are not black and white and a balancing of chances and challenges needs to be done. One prominent example are the R&D around permanent magnet applications.

Recent accelerator upgrades show that it is possible to significantly save grid energy by using permanent magnets instead of the classical electromagnets. At DESY the upgrade of PETRA foresees a new magnet lattice to achieve low beam emittance, and with the given parameters only permanent magnets allow to realise such lattice.

• ESRF:	before upgrade after upgrade	16.9 GWh / year 8.5 GWh / year	↓ J.Chavanne, Permanent accelerator magnets for light sources, 5th ESSRI Workshop 2019, https://indico.psi.ch/event/6754/contributions/18013/
• PSI:	SLS SLS2.0	6.4 GWh / year 2.6 GWh / year	↓ M.Seidel, Technologies for Sustainable Accelerators, First iFAST annual meeting, 2022, https://indico.cern.ch/event/1138690/contributions/4782721/
• HZB:	BESSY II BESSY III	5.1 GWh / year < 1.3 GWh / year	↓ J.Völker, Overview permanent magnets at accelerator facilities, iFAST REE workshop 2023, https://indico.desy.de/event/35655/timetable/#20230206.detailed

Figure 16: Electrical energy savings due to the use of permanent magnets at different RIs ([8,9,10])

But advantages of permanent magnets don't come for free. Key materials in permanent magnets are Rare Earth Elements (and cobalt), which are mostly mined and processed in China under precarious conditions for people and environment [11]. Additionally, the recycling of these materials is not yet established in an industrial scale and is just beginning [12,13]. In the realm of I.FAST work package 11 Task 1 Sustainable Concepts and Technologies for RIs a workshop on the criticality of Rare Earth Elements [14] was organised. The workshop raised awareness for these problems and explored ways for solutions and suggestions how the accelerator community can contribute to tackle these challenges.

In the last decade, the sustainability of materials and technical components has come under increasing scrutiny. Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) examine the evolution of a product from cradle to grave. NGO’s help to investigate ecological and sociological conditions in mining and processing countries, especially for magnet materials in China and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). Teams at many European institutions are working on LCA for REE [11, 15]. They identified the mining, processing and recycling as most problematic processes. Research institutes like Fraunhofer, HU Pforzheim [16] and many others [17] are working together with suppliers and industries in joined projects for finding solutions in recycling.

▪ Climate Change Potential (Global Warming)	GWP	kg CO ₂ eq.
▪ Eutrophication Potential (Over-fertilization)	EP	kg P eq./kg N eq.
▪ Photochemical Ozone Depletion Potential (Summersmog)	POCP	kg Ethene eq.
▪ Ozone Depletion Potential (Ozone hole)	ODP	kg CFC-11 eq.
▪ Acidification Potential (Acid rain)	AP	kg SO ₂ eq.
▪ Human toxicity	HTP	kg 1,4-DCB eq.
▪ Ecotoxicity	FAETP / MAETP / TETP	kg 1,4-DCB eq.
▪ Abiotic Resource Depletion (Resource scarcity)	ADP	kg Cu eq.
▪ Water scarcity		m ³ world eq.
▪ Land use		m ² a
▪	

Figure 17: Categories of environmental impact assessments important for permanent magnets.

REE are associated with many negative ecological, environmental and social impacts in producing and processing countries. The workshop pointed out that a technical component must be considered not only from the point of view of energy efficiency. The entire life cycle has to be kept in mind. Components and materials used in a facility should be selected, whenever technically possible, for low environmental impact. Lifecycle management of components is important in this context, for example developing strategies for renewal and repair of faulty components instead of immediate disposal. The use of helium (as a scarce resource) for accelerator and research applications, the minimization of its losses and methods for recovery represent another topic. With the carbon footprint analysis a metrics was developed for assessment of the overall impact of a facility or a process.

The results, chances and challenges identified for the sustainable procurement of permanent magnets need to be discussed and developed further – as a quick and easy solution is not yet available. Therefore a focus was set on communicating the workshops results and discuss them at several workshops and conferences including with industry contacts.

Examples of communication and discussion of the workshop results

article	A.Klumpp, D.Völker, M.Seidel, Rare earths for permanent magnets: blessing or curse?, Accelerating News, March 13, 2023, online
article	Budrikis, Z., Völker, D. Making science sustainable at DESY. Nat Rev Phys 5, 370–371 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1038/s42254-023-00597-w
Conference talk	Klumpp, A.; Völker, D., Challenges in applications of permanent magnets in accelerators on the example of the major accelerator upgrade at DESY; REPM - 27TH INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON RARE EARTH AND FUTURE PERMANENT MAGNETS AND THEIR APPLICATIONS; 03./07.09.2023, University of Birmingham); https://uobevents.eventsair.com/repm2023/programme
Conference talk	Klumpp, A., Critical Materials and Life Cycle Thinking; Low Emittance Ring –Permanent Magnets Workshop; November 14th2023 / Trieste, Italy; online: https://indico.cells.es/event/1373/timetable/#20231115.detailed
Conference session	Völker, D., How to assess the (environmental) impact of RIs?; 3rd I.FAST annual meeting; Paris, April 18, 2024, https://indico.cern.ch/event/1357302/overview
Conference session	Völker, D., Life cycle evaluation, 7th ESSRI conference (Energy Madrid, September 26, 2024, https://agenda.ciemat.es/event/4431/timetable/#20240926

As a result of these discussions further developments were started, namely on methods and content of any kind of environmental assessments. Footprints, LCAs or environmental impact studies help to understand the impact science has on global challenges like climate change and others. They help to identify the fields for improvement and make progress countable. It also helps raising awareness amongst scientists and stirs more attention to better solutions already in the design process of new and updated RIs.

Many evaluations [18,19,20] have been conducted lately and there is a common understanding and motivation to develop these approaches further and to design science specific methodologies. So far, some evaluations look at everything - others focus on the big parts. Some look only at CO₂ – others at all Greenhouse Gases and yet others take the whole environmental footprint into account or even sustainability measures outside of the ecological realm. And everybody is using different databases and sources for the respective conversion factors.

Further work in this realm shall be dedicated to give an overview of what has been done so far and to analyze the approaches in terms of methodology, scope, parameters and databases used in order to

stir the discussion on and development of commonly agreed metrics and processes to facilitate the evaluation of proposals and allow a fair comparison between them.

Figure 18: Example of a detailed LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) of power supplies (DESY)

Fig. 19: Example of the LCA setup to compare the construction of the Compact Linear Collider (CLIC) and the International Linear Collider (ILC).

7 Permanent Combined Function Magnets for Light Sources, B.Shepherd

The main deliverable of Task 11.3 is a combined-function dipole-quadrupole magnet based on permanent magnets (PMs), with coils providing a low level of adjustment on both the dipole and quadrupole fields. The magnet should have parameters suitable for use on the Diamond-II synchrotron light source upgrade. The parameters listed in Table 2 have been agreed with DLS.

Table 2: Magnet parameters

Parameter	Dipole	Quadrupole
Central field, gradient	0.695 T	32.4 T/m
Magnetic length	870 mm	
Integrated dipole, gradient	0.605 T.m	28.2 T
Good field region radius	7 mm	
Field, gradient quality	5×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}
Tuning range	$\pm 2.5\%$	$\pm 2.5\%$
Minimum vertical aperture between main poles	13 mm	
Minimum vertical aperture between auxiliary poles	24 mm	

Maximum height of magnet yoke	563 mm	
Distance between base of magnet support and beam axis	475 mm	
Maximum total length of magnet	931 mm	

7.1 Initial Magnet Design

The magnetic design was carried out at UKRI using the Opera finite-element analysis software package. The design is based on the concept of a single-sided dipole-quadrupole. Figure shows a schematic of the design with the different components labelled.

The PM blocks are made from NdFeB, grade 40EH, with a remanent field of 1.32 T at 20°C. The yoke and poles are made from XC06 low-carbon magnetic steel. Thermal shunts are made from a FeNi alloy with a negative temperature coefficient, in order to compensate for the temperature variation of the PM blocks and keep the field constant around room temperature. The pole tips are curved to keep the dipole field constant along the curved beam axis.

Figure 20: Labeled image of 2D PM DQ design (left) and 3D model (right).

The pole profiles have been optimised to produce the specified dipole and quadrupole fields, and to maximise the field quality across the good field region. Corrector coils have been added to the poles to produce the required tuning range in both field and gradient. The thickness of the thermal shunts have been optimised to minimise the variation of field with temperature in the range 20-23°C. For the nominal model, the field and gradient quality are within specification in this temperature range.

Following the production of a magnetic design, Kyma carried out some work to produce a conceptual mechanical design. The main issues arise from the large forces between the PM blocks and the ferromagnetic steel pieces. The sub-assemblies must be held together against these forces during assembly, and the whole structure must be rigid when the construction is complete. The left-hand side of Figure shows a schematic of the overall design.

Figure 21: Mechanical design of DQ magnet (left); close-up showing gap spacers (right)

Small non-magnetic spacers are inserted between the main poles, and between the main and auxiliary poles. This ensures that the poles can be positioned with the required precision for the specified field quality.

The magnet has been broken up into sub-assemblies, separating the four poles and the back part of the yoke. The PM blocks are glued onto aluminium blocks to enable them to be attached to the poles. At each stage of construction, the ferromagnetic sub-assemblies are built using a specialised assembly rig with hand wheels and screw jacks, so that the position of each piece is tightly controlled.

7.2 REDESIGN

Unfortunately, the cost for the required amount of PM material was outside the available funds for the Task, and we were forced to seek alternative solutions. UKRI identified some spare PM blocks that were unused from a previous project (the CLARA modulator undulators), and started work on a second version of the design (HEPTO v2). The overall design concept is the same as for v1; however, an extra row of PM blocks has been added above/below the main pole to achieve the desired field strength. The magnet blocks (dimensions 60x83x37mm) are not glued together into large blocks, but held in a non-magnetic “ice-cube tray” structure.

A similar approach was required with the thermal shunt material (FeNi alloy); this was only available from the manufacturer in large quantities; we were able to source a smaller amount of material from colleagues at Soleil in France, which meant that the available budget was not exceeded.

The design of the magnet has been optimised using Opera 2D and 3D magnetic models. Figure 22: Labelled image of Opera 3D model of HEPTO design (left); thick black arrows represent the direction of magnetisation of permanent magnet blocks. The individual PM blocks are shown on the right, and the ‘ice-cube tray’ structure to contain them is shown in the centre of the figure. gives an overview of the main components of the magnet.

Figure 22: Labelled image of Opera 3D model of HEPTO design (left); thick black arrows represent the direction of magnetisation of permanent magnet blocks. The individual PM blocks are shown on the right, and the ‘ice-cube tray’ structure to contain them is shown in the centre of the figure.

The v2 design is capable of achieving the field requirements of the DQ magnets for the Diamond-II upgrade. It produces the target integrated dipole and gradient fields, and the nominal integrated field quality $\Delta B/B$ is less than the requirement of 5×10^{-4} with an optimised pole profile.

The mechanical design (Figure) is has been completed; during this period, we have focused on adapting the design to accommodate the change from custom-made PM blocks to pre-made ‘spare’ blocks. Additionally, a mechanical shimming concept has been developed enabling more relaxed initial tolerances on the main and auxiliary poles.

1. Threaded rods will be inserted into the auxiliary poles to enable horizontal adjustment of the auxiliary pole tips.
2. Screws are inserted between the auxiliary pole and upper/lower aluminium plate. Brass shims can be added or removed to adjust the auxiliary poles’ vertical position.
3. Two set screws are used to move the aluminium plate which holds the magnets and the top main pole horizontally. The bottom main pole serves as a reference and will have no adjustment.
4. The top main pole can be adjusted vertically using screws and brass shims.

Figure 23: Mechanical design of HEPTO v2 magnet including vacuum chamber (left); location of mechanical shimming rods (right).

Another aspect of the mechanical design revolves around the magnetic forces present during and after assembly. In the v2 design, horizontal yoke arms have been added to provide additional mechanical support. Aluminium gap spacers are used to fix the vertical gap between the main pole arms and prevent unwanted deformation of the poles.

8 Conclusions and Key Recommendations

In this work package of the I.FAST Project several concepts and key technologies to enhance sustainability of accelerator driven research facilities were studied. We formulate the following recommendations that emerged throughout the project:

8.1 GENERAL

- Include sustainability in the early planning stages of new facilities. This will make it easier to implement sustainability and will support economic solutions.
- Things that seem straightforward, like excess heat recycling, may in the end turn out to demand quite complex implementations. Make sure to have all stakeholders in the discussions at an early stage.
- However, also for existing facilities sustainable solutions can be retrofitted, and CERN has demonstrated impressive examples like implementing pulsed magnet circuits in the north area.
- While energy consumption is the most significant aspect for RI's, there are many other topics that deserve more attention, ranging from water and helium consumption over critical materials and life cycle considerations for components up to the carbon footprint related to construction of entire infrastructures.

8.2 ENERGY EFFICIENT TECHNOLOGIES

The energy consumption from the grid is often significant for large accelerator driven research infrastructures. The following technologies will play a key role for reducing energy consumption.

- Superconducting technologies, both RF structures and magnets, can provide energy efficient solutions for particle accelerators. Through the application of high temperature superconductors (HTS), magnets and resonators may operate at higher cryogenic temperature, resulting in an improvement of cryogenic efficiency by factors. Also magnets for moderate fields can be realized with HTS coils to save power, and studies are progressing to retrofit existing normalconducting magnets that need high power with compact HTS coils.
- Magnets equipped with permanent magnet material don't need electric power. The technology has advanced significantly for light sources, where the main focus is to design compact magnets for low emittance lattices. A welcome side effect for these new light sources is the reduction of energy consumption.
- RF sources are an important element in the power conversion chain from grid to beam. In particular for klystrons but also for solid state amplifiers significant efforts are invested to increase the energy efficiency. New accelerator projects should aim at utilizing efficient RF sources.

8.3 MATERIALS AND LIFE CYCLE MANAGEMENT

This is a relatively new topic for accelerator RI's and WP11 of I.FAST has contributed significantly to introduce the topic in the field

- Accelerator components should be designed in a way as to ease repair and refurbishment, and also the recycling of the used materials at end of life.
- Critical materials like those based on rare earths, or a high environmental impact in general require specific considerations. Ideally the production path of such materials or components manufactured from them should be certified.

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